

Rapid dissolution of larger amounts of rock and ore samples by microwave digestion for the estimation of gold by ICP-MS for geochemical prospecting studies

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A microwave dissolution method for the determination of gold in sample weight as high as 10 g has been described. The gold concentrations in several field samples and gold reference samples are estimated using ICP-MS after microwave dissolution. ^{103}Rh is used as an internal standard. The gold values obtained compare well with the certified values. The average values obtained on the replicate determinations are within 10% RSD with comparable accuracy. The efficiencies of the microwave dissolution and the open-acid-digestion for the extraction of gold in a few field samples are compared. Microwave dissolution is found to be more efficient apart from giving faster dissolution. The detection limit of gold is found to be 0.02 ng/g using this method.

It is well known that gold occurs at a very low concentration and distributes heterogeneously in rocks and minerals and other geological materials. Consequently relatively larger sample sizes (>10 g) are typically processed to obtain representative concentrations¹. The size of the sample taken for gold estimations ranges from 5 to 10 g or more, compared to the usual 0.1 to 1 g used for estimation of other trace elements. Although analytical technique such as ICP-MS is capable of determining gold at ng/ml level^{2,3}, sample preparation still remains the limiting factor. Generally two acid mixtures, aqua regia and HBr-Br₂ are used for sample decomposition after roasting the sample at 650° to destroy sulfides and organic matter, before gold is estimated using instrumental techniques, such as atomic absorption spectrometry^{4,5}. Recently, some workers⁶ have used microwave digestion for the estimation of platinum group elements and gold. But the sample size used was only 0.5 g which may not be sufficient to compensate for the heterogenous distribution of gold in geological samples.

The authors have described here a method of dissolution of rock and ore samples using commercial microwave oven followed by the estimation of gold using ICP-MS.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary studies were carried out to find out the optimum conditions for the efficient digestion of the sample for a near quantitative extraction of gold from the sample by the systematic variation of various parameters of microwave digestion such as power, pressure and temperature, keeping the amount of sample at 10 g and the volume of the reagents constant. The operating conditions of the microwave oven are given in Table 2.

Table 1. Operating parameters of ICP-MS

Argon plasma :	
RF power, Forward, W	1300
Reflected, W	<5
Argon gas flow, coolant, dm ³ min ⁻¹	12
Auxillary, dm ³ min ⁻¹	0.60
Nebulizer, dm ³ min ⁻¹	0.70
Nebulizer type	Standard Meinhard
Spray chamber	Scott-type, water-cooled
Ion sampling :	
Sampling cone	Nickel sampler (NiCone™) with 1.0 mm orifice
Skimmer cone	Nickel skimmer (NiCone™) with 0.75 mm orifice
Sampling distance	10 mm from load coil and fixed
Sample uptake rate	0.8 ml min ⁻¹
Ion lens setting	Optimized on ^{103}Rh
Vacuum :	
Expansion stage, mbar	2.2
Intermediate stage, mbar	<10 ⁻⁴
Analyzer stage, mbar	2 × 10 ⁻⁶
Data acquisition :	
Quantitative mass scanning range, m/z	100-199
Skipped mass regions, m/z	104-195
Sweeps	120
Dwell time, μs	600
Channels	2048
Total analysis time per run	20 s approx.

However, the capacity and design of the digestion vessels in most of the commercial microwave ovens do not permit digestion of more than 10 g samples. The parameters (Table 2) gave more efficient extraction of gold from the

Table 2. Conditions for microwave digestion of the rock and ore samples

Power output, W	900
Power duration time, min	25
Maximum pressure, psi	381
Maximum temperature, °C	205

samples and hence all the samples were digested under these conditions. The microwave digestion of 10 g samples followed by determination of gold using ICP-MS was examined for its potential use in gold exploration studies. The concentrations of gold obtained by the method described are presented in Table 3. It can be seen that the recoveries of gold in majority of the cases are above 90%. The results

Table 3. Concentrations of gold obtained by ICP-MS in different gold reference materials and in-house standard after 10 g samples were subjected to microwave dissolution in comparison with certified values wherever applicable

Sample no.*	Rock type	Au ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	
		Present study ^d	Reference
GAu 11 ^a	Stream sediment	12.0 \pm 2 ng/g	11.40 ^e ng/g
GAu 12 ^a	Stream sediment	25.0 \pm 3 ng/g	21.50 ^e ng/g
GAu 13 ^a	Soil	61.0 \pm 5 ng/g	50.00 ^e ng/g
GAu 14 ^a	Soil	0.12 \pm 0.02 $\mu\text{g/g}$	0.10 ^e $\mu\text{g/g}$
GTS-1 ^b	Gold tailing sample	0.32 \pm 0.03 $\mu\text{g/g}$	0.346 ^f $\mu\text{g/g}$
CH-3 ^b	Gold bearing sulphide ore	1.38 \pm 0.14 $\mu\text{g/g}$	1.40 ^g $\mu\text{g/g}$
MA-2b ^b	Gold ore	2.36 \pm 0.22 $\mu\text{g/g}$	2.39 ^g $\mu\text{g/g}$
CCU-1b ^b	Copper concentrate	5.60 \pm 0.50 $\mu\text{g/g}$	5.89 ^g $\mu\text{g/g}$
AJ ore ^c	Banded iron formation	7.89 \pm 0.32 $\mu\text{g/g}$	9.31 ^h $\mu\text{g/g}$
PTM 1 ^b	Noble metal copper nickel matte	1.81 \pm 0.05 $\mu\text{g/g}$	1.80 ^f $\mu\text{g/g}$

*Source: ^aIGGE, China; ^bCCRMP, Canada; ^cField sample, Karnataka, India; ^dAverage values of three determinations are given in all cases; ^eRef. 5; ^fW. S. Bowman certified reference materials, CCRMP 90-1E (1990) 63; ^gW. S. Bowman certified reference materials, CCRMP 94-1E (1994) 76; ^hNGRI value.

presented in Table 4 suggest that even microwave dissolution without using HF cannot extract the gold encapsulated in silicate structure. Addition of HF will facilitate breaking of the silicate structure and liberation of gold grains leading to quantitative recoveries. For these studies, complete dissolution of the samples (5 g) was achieved by using aqua regia, bromine, HF and HClO₄ with and without microwave digestion and the results are compared. Microwave digestion is found superior both in terms of speed and efficiency (Table 4). The recovery of silver in these investigations was found to be as good as that of gold. The results of the recoveries of silver and platinum group elements (PGE)

Table 4. A comparative presentation of concentrations of gold ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in reference samples and field samples by two decomposition procedures using microwave digestion

Sample no.*	Aqua regia leach (Partial dissolution)	HF and HClO ₄ Aqua regia, Br ₂ (Complete dissolution)		Certified value
		Open	Closed	
PTM-1	1.70	1.80	1.82	1.8 ^a
PAP-S-5F-97	0.21	0.38	0.38	-
AJN-B-96	8.74	11.77	12.12	-
AJN-A-96	8.78	12.80	13.46	-
SN-5	1.66	1.90	2.00	-
AG-1	8.91	10.11	10.27	-
AJN-16-96	0.44	0.50	0.56	-
PAP-S-40-97	0.23	0.28	0.28	-
SN-3	1.46	1.70	1.68	-
GXR-1	3.00	3.10	3.28	3.30 ^b

*All samples except PTM-1 (CCRMP, Canada) and GXR-1 (USGS, USA), are iron formation samples from Chitradurga area, Karnataka, India.

(-) = Not available

^aW. S. Bowman certified reference materials (1990) CCRMP 90-1E, 63; ^bK. Govindaraju, Compilation of working values and sample descriptions for 383 geostandards, Special Issue, *Geostand. Newslett.*, 1994, 18.

from rocks and ores, were published by one of authors elsewhere⁷.

Generally contamination of gold in sample solutions from the acids and other reagents used was not found. On the other hand, cross-contamination of gold due to memory effect of the previous sample was observed during ICP-MS analysis. This memory problem was overcome by aspirating 5% HNO₃ for 4 min after the analysis of every sample². The contributions from double-distilled water, acids and other reagents used in these investigations, gave very low blank values for gold with an average count rate of about 30 counts/s as against a signal of 10⁵ counts/s normally obtained for 100 g ml⁻¹ of gold. The detection limit of gold is found to be 0.02 ng ml⁻¹ (ppb) which is extremely low and much lower than the average crustal abundance of gold. This suggests that ICP-MS can detect and determine gold concentrations at its natural abundance levels in rocks, ore and related geological materials.

In an attempt to compare the high efficiency of microwave digestion with conventional open-acid digestion for the extraction of gold, a few iron formation samples from Karnataka area were dissolved using both open-acid digestion and closed-microwave digestion procedures, and the concentrations of gold were estimated by ICP-MS. The com-

parative results (Table 5) suggest that the microwave digestion procedure is more rapid and efficient. The average value obtained in replicate analyses of different samples in these investigations (Tables 3–5) are within 10% RSD (relative standard deviation).

Table 5 Comparative concentrations of gold ($\mu\text{g/g}$) obtained by ICP-MS, after 10 g ore samples (iron formations) were dissolved using both classical open and closed microwave dissolution methods*

Sample no	Open digestion method	Closed digestion method
TKG-270	1.04 \pm 0.06	2.76 \pm 0.13
TKG-261	0.90 \pm 0.06	2.03 \pm 0.10
TKG-187	0.06 \pm 0.01	0.12 \pm 0.01
TKG-263	0.37 \pm 0.03	1.56 \pm 0.10
TKG-277	0.02 \pm 0.01	0.04 \pm 0.01
TKG-321	0.02 \pm 0.01	0.06 \pm 0.01

*All are iron formation field samples from Kunchiguanalu, Karnataka, India

Experimental

The ICP-MS instrument used was a PlasmaQuad PQ1 (VG Elemental Analysis, UK) controlled by an IBM PC-XT microcomputer and associated software (issue 3.1). The other details of the instrument and the operating parameters chosen are given in Table 1. These parameters are kept constant throughout the study. In order to compensate for the signal drift due to changes in nebulizer efficiency, gradual clogging of the torch and interface, matrix induced suppressions and for minimizing mass discrimination effects, and space-charge effects, rhodium (^{103}Rh) was used as an internal standard. The concentrations of rhodium were found to be present at insignificant levels ($< 20 \text{ ng/g}$) in the samples investigated in the present study using semi-quantitative survey analysis⁸.

All dissolutions were done using a computer-controlled QWAVE 3000 microwave laboratory oven (Questron Corporation, USA) with fume exhaust, rotating carousel, PFA lining and 10-multiply 120 ml high pressure digestion vessels capable of operation at upto 635 psi and 230°. This unit had a pressure and temperature monitor system with feed-back facility to enable computer control of both pressure and temperature within the vessels. The operating conditions are given in Table 2.

The details of the gold reference samples and field samples are given in the respective Tables. The field samples (10 kg) were reduced to sample powder (600 g) of 230 mesh, using the procedure described elsewhere¹. All the solutions were prepared using double-distilled water. AnalaRTM grade

acids and other reagents were used. Gold and rhodium solutions ($1000 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) were obtained from Alfa products.

Microwave digestion procedure : The sample (10 g) was taken in a 100-ml porcelain crucible and roasted in a muffle furnace at 650° for 30 min. After cooling, the sample was transferred into all-PFA microwave digestion vessel, then freshly prepared aqua regia (20 ml) was added and the contents were mixed thoroughly before capping the vessel. The samples were digested in the microwave oven using the operating conditions (Table 2). The microwave oven carousel can hold 10 vessels at a time. Most runs consisted of samples and one reagent blank. When fewer samples were digested, the remaining vessels were filled with aqua regia (30 ml). It is very important to fill the microwave carousel with all 10 vessels because the delivered power is always calculated for a full carousel.

After cooling the vessels under tap water the contents were quantitatively transferred to 250-ml volumetric flask and filtered through Whatman No. 41 filter paper after making the volume. To the filtrate (10 ml) was added $10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ ^{103}Rh solution (1 ml) to act as an internal standard and the volume was made upto 100 ml keeping the acidity at 1 M HCl in the final solution. In the case of dissolutions involving use of HF, after the microwave program, the sample was transferred quantitatively to a teflon beaker and silica was expelled on a hotplate (210°) after adding sufficient amount of HF and the residue was dissolved in 1 : 1 HCl (25 ml) and the volume made upto 250 ml. This solution (10 ml) was diluted to 100 ml after the addition of $10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ Rh solution (1 ml) for ICP-MS analysis keeping the acidity at 1 M HCl.

Open digestion procedure : The sample powder (10 g) was taken in 250-ml Corning beakers. Freshly prepared aqua regia (50 ml) was added and the contents were thoroughly mixed and kept overnight for digestion after proper covering. Then the beaker was covered with watch glasses and heated on a hotplate (200°) over a period of 5–6 h under reflux conditions with periodic addition of sufficient aqua regia. Aqua regia was added in between to enable maximum extraction of gold and to maintain minimum volume of about 50 ml at any given time. The total dissolution of 5g sample using acid mixture of aqua regia, Br_2 , HF and HClO_4 was carried out in 250-ml teflon beaker. After cooling to room temperature, the sample solution for ICP-MS analysis was prepared as in the case of microwave digestion procedure.

ICP-MS analysis : The ICP-MS operating parameters are given in Table 1. ^{103}Rh and ^{197}Au isotopes were used for analysis. The instrument was calibrated using 10, 50

and 100 ng ml⁻¹ Au calibration standards. The sample solutions were analyzed in mass scanning mode. The nebulizer-spray chamber system was washed with 5% HNO₃ for 4 min in between the samples to remove the memory effects noticed especially with Au. Data acquisition and reduction were done under instrument software control.

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